

Formulation And Development Of Transdermal Patches Of Curcumin

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aimed to develop and optimize curcumin-loaded transdermal patches to enhance its therapeutic potential while addressing its poor bioavailability. **Materials & Methods:** A central composite design was used to evaluate the effects of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), ethyl cellulose (EC), and di-n-butyl phthalate (DBP) on patch performance, focusing on drug release and swelling index. **Results:** Preformulation studies confirmed the drug's authenticity and properties, including UV absorption maxima at 425 nm. The optimized patch (F5: 300 mg HPMC, 100 mg EC, 1 mL DBP) showed 83.2% drug release and a swelling index of 24.10 ± 1.4 . **Conclusion:** These findings suggest that curcumin transdermal patches have significant potential as an alternative therapy for managing inflammation and allergies. Further clinical studies are recommended to validate their therapeutic efficacy and establish their role in improving the delivery of herbal drugs like curcumin.

Keywords: Curcumin, Transdermal drug delivery, Central composite design, Swelling index, Drug release, Herbal drug delivery, Bioavailability enhancement, Preformulation studies, Quadratic modelling.

INTRODUCTION

Curcumin, a polyphenol derived from turmeric, exhibits a wide range of therapeutic properties, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, neuroprotective, and antimicrobial activities, making it a promising agent for managing numerous health conditions. Its anti-inflammatory effects help mitigate chronic diseases like arthritis, cardiovascular diseases, and neurodegenerative disorders, while its antioxidant properties protect cells from oxidative damage, a key factor in aging and many diseases. Despite these benefits, curcumin's clinical application is hindered by poor bioavailability due to low absorption, rapid metabolism, and systemic elimination. Strategies to enhance its bioavailability, such as combining it with bioavailability enhancers like piperine, have shown significant promise. Curcumin is utilized worldwide in various forms, including capsules, ointments, energy drinks, and cosmetics, and its safety profile has been affirmed in

clinical trials, even at high doses. While its therapeutic potential is vast, ongoing research and clinical trials are crucial to fully establish curcumin's efficacy and optimize its application in human health [1- 2].

The transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) delivers medication through the skin into the bloodstream, offering controlled release, improved compliance, and reduced side effects by bypassing the gastrointestinal tract and first-pass metabolism. Comprising a backing layer, drug reservoir, controlled-release membrane, and adhesive, TDDS ensures consistent drug delivery through the skin's stratum corneum. It is widely used for pain management (e.g., fentanyl, lidocaine), hormone therapy, contraception, nicotine replacement, cardiovascular conditions, Alzheimer's, and neurological disorders. Despite challenges like limited drug types and skin irritation, advances in technology enhance its efficacy. Emerging uses include transdermal curcumin for psoriasis and

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simvastatin for lipid management, showcasing TDDS's versatility and therapeutic potential [3-6].

This study aims to develop and optimize curcumin-loaded transdermal patches using a central composite design. The effects of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), ethyl cellulose (EC), and di-n-butyl phthalate (DBP) on key attributes such as drug release and swelling index were systematically evaluated. The preformulation studies were conducted to ensure the authenticity and compatibility of curcumin with the selected polymers and excipients [7-10].

By addressing the challenges associated with curcumin's bioavailability, this research explores the potential of transdermal patches as an alternative to conventional dosage forms. The findings aim to contribute to the growing field of herbal drug delivery systems and pave the way for future clinical studies to establish curcumin-based transdermal patches as a viable therapeutic option for managing inflammation, allergies, and other conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Procurement of drug and polymers

Table No. 1 Procurement of Drug

S. No.	Name	Category	Procurement
1	Curcumin	Anti-inflammatory, Anti-oxidant	Semi labs, Bangalore
2	HPMC	Polymer	Qualikems
3	Ethyl Cellulose	Polymer	Loba chemie
4	Dibutyl phthalate	Permeation enhancer	Alpha Chemika
5	Ethanol	Solvent	Loba chemie
6	Distilled water	Solvent	Loba chemie

Preformulation studies

Identification of drug

Preformulation is a group of studies which generally carried out for identification and compatibility study. It focuses on the physicochemical properties of a new drug candidate that could affect the drug performance and the development of a dosage form. Preformulation studies were generally carried out for identification and compatibility studies of API and excipients.

Melting point

Melting point is one of the identification tests for organic compounds. The melting point of the drug was determined by capillary melting point method using melting point apparatus (Tempo, India). The drug was filled in a thin-walled capillary tube, with sealed one end. The capillary was then placed in melting point apparatus and the temperature of the apparatus was gradually increased. The temperature range over which the drug melts was observed.

FTIR and UV Spectrophotometry analysis

The FTIR studies of curcumin were performed over the 4000– 400 cm⁻¹ wavelength regions at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Attenuated total reflectance is employed to analyse the IR transmission spectra and trace the distinguishing peaks, sample in the ratio 1:100 is mixed with KBr for analysis by FTIR spectrophotometer.[20].Lambda max is the wavelength of light in the ultraviolet region at which maximum absorbance is exhibited by the compound. Sample was dissolved in methanol to prepare stock solution and scan in UV spectrophotometer.

Solubility studies

The solubility studies of drug in aqueous and non-aqueous phases are the important properties during formulation consideration and also Sbehavior and transport of drugs in the body. Equilibrium solubility was determined at room temperature, for this, systems of each solvent (DW, Methanol, Ethanol & PBS pH

7.4) were taken individually in volumetric flask and drug was added gradually in each solvent and vigorously shaken on shaker. As the saturation point was reached a pinch of drug was added to it and the flask was shaken for 15min and placed in the flask shaker for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs it was removed and observed. Since un-dissolved drug was found it was kept for 24hrs undisturbed. After 24 hrs, the solution was filtered and diluted suitably with reagent blank and absorbance was taken against reagent blank and recorded.

Drug- excipients compatibility studies

Drug excipients compatibility study was done by using I.R. spectroscopy different mixtures of drug and carrier were prepared and analysed by I.R. in the range of 400- 4000 cm⁻¹. Small amount of sample was taken and analysed by placing it in powder sample compartment and it was check for any interaction between drug and excipients.

Preparation of standard calibration curves

10 mg of Curcumin was weighed accurately and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved

in small amount of ethanol, after that volume was made up to 100 ml with ethanol so as to obtain stock solution of 100 µg/ml. Stock solution was taken in aliquots of 0.1 ml, 0.2 ml, upto 0.5 ml in to a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume was made up to the mark with ethanol. The solutions were filtered through Whatman filter paper no. 1 and filtrate was analyzed at λ_{max} 425nm using UV visible spectrophotometer. Methanol was used as blank solution. The standard curve was plotted between absorbance and concentration.

Optimization of prepared batches by quality of design

Drug permeation and mechanical properties of the film are affected by the concentration of HPMC, EC and permeation enhancer. Thus, in order to study the consequence of responses i.e., swelling index of film and drug release and optimization of formulation factors, Central composite statistical design was chosen. The designed combinations of excipients by the software were mentioned in Table No. 2

Table No.2 Optimization of prepared batches by quality of design

Std	Run	Factor 1 A:HPMC (in mg)	Factor 2 B:EC (in mg)	Factor 3 C:DBP (in ml)
10	1	468.179	100	1
1	2	200	50	0.5
12	3	300	184.09	1
4	4	400	150	0.5
15	5	300	100	1
14	6	300	100	1.8409
17	7	300	100	1
11	8	300	15.9104	1
5	9	200	50	1.5
2	10	400	50	0.5
13	11	300	100	0.159104
3	12	200	150	0.5
7	13	200	150	1.5
6	14	400	50	1.5
8	15	400	150	1.5
9	16	131.821	100	1
16	17	300	100	1

Evaluation of prepared patch

Folding endurance

The patches were sliced into required dimension (4 cm X 2 cm). Then they were folded at the same location repeatedly until it breaks. The number of times the film is folded without cracking or breaking is calculated.[21]

Tensile strength

The strip was clamped at the static end and was attached to the movable rod on a railing with the help of a clip. The weights were gradually added to the pan to increase the pull force till the film was cut. The elongation was determined simultaneously by noting the distance travelled by the pointer, before break of the film, on the graph paper. The weight required to break the film was noted as the break force. [22]

The tensile strength was calculated using Allen's formula.

Thickness

The thickness was measured at six different places using an Electronic Digital Micrometer and the mean Value was calculated.[22]

Drug content

A formulated patch having 15.21cm² area was cut into small pieces and transferred into a graduated glass stoppered flask, which contained 100ml of mixture of chloroform and methanol in the ratio of 1:1, maintained at 45-50°C. It was closed and shaken vigorously for 24 hours period in a shaker. The solution was filtered and the amount of drug present in the filtrate was determined by using SHIMADZU UV-1700 spectrophotometer at 241nm. Similarly, blank solution was prepared using a dummy patch. The procedure was carried out in duplicate to determine the drug content. The following procedure was carried out induplicate to determine the drug content.[23]

Percentage moisture content

Moisture content can influence the mechanical strength and drug release behaviour of the transdermal therapeutic systems and therefore, in the present study determination of the moisture of the formulated patch was estimated by keeping the patch under vacuum desiccation until constant weights were obtained. The percentage moisture content of the patch was calculated by the following formula.[22]

Percentage moisture content = (Initial weight- Final weight) /Initial weight

Percentage moisture uptake

The weighed films kept in a desiccator at room temperature for 24hrs was taken out and exposed to 75% relative humidity (a saturated solution of sodium chloride) in a desiccator until a constant weight for the film was calculated as the difference between final and initial weight with respect to initial weight. [24]

Percentage moisture uptake = (final weight- initial weight)/ final weight

In vitro drug release studies

The prepared films were attached onto the dialysis membrane and further adhered to the franz diffusion cell. Consequently, the surface from where the drug permeates having 0.785 cm² area was facing towards receptor compartment. The receptor compartment contains phosphate buffer of 7.4 pH maintained at 37 degree centigrade which is magnetically swirled. At programmed timings, 5 mL samples were taken out and equal volume of fresh buffer was replaced. The samples withdrawn were diluted with ethanol and then analysed spectrophotometrically at 416 nm.[25]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies

Organoleptic Properties

Various tests were used to analyse the organoleptic properties of curcumin. Table 3 shows results of Mayer's test, Wagner's test.

Table 3 Mayer's test, Wagner's test

Test	Result	Observation
Mayer's Reagent Test	Light Yellowish ppt. was formed	Presence of Alkaloid
Wagner's Test	Dark Brown ppt. was formed	Presence of Alkaloid

Melting point

Melting point of the drug was found to be similar to the reported value which proved that the received drug samples meet the reported properties. Any impurity, if present, will cause variation in the melting point of a given drug substance. Reported melting point of curcumin is 183°C. Melting point was determined using capillary method and it was found that drug start melting at 179° C and completely melted at 181 °C. From the above test it was found that the sample drug complies with the standard test of curcumin.

FTIR study was performed on Drug and different polymers for determination of functional groups that will describe the identity.

Table 4 IR peaks of Curcumin

Sample	Element
3628cm-1	OH group
2931 cm-1	CH stretching
1718 cm-1	C=O stretching
1656 cm-1	C=C stretching
1314 cm-1	C-O
1193 cm-1	O-H bending
817 cm-1	C-H vibration

Figure 2 IR spectra of HPMC

Determination of Lambda max

UV spectrophotometer shows maximum absorption of curcumin at 425nm shown in Figure 4

Figure 3 Lambda max determination of Curcumin

Solubility determination of curcumin was done using different solvents like Ethanol, Benzene, Dimethylformamide, Acetone, Ethyl acetate and water, results is shown in Table 6

Table 5 Quantitative solubility of Curcumin

Element	Soluble
Ethanol	Soluble
Benzene	Insoluble
Dimethyl Formamide	Partially Soluble
Acetone	Soluble
Ethyl Acetate	Soluble
Water	Insoluble

Figure no. 5 Calibration curve of Curcumin**Evaluation of prepared patch****Drug- excipients compatibility studies**

Compatibility studies was carried out using FTIR. Blend containing Drug, polymer and permeation enhancer was used for FTIR analysis. Results shows that there is no interaction between drug and excipients.

Figure 4 IR spectra of Blend**Preparation of standard calibration curve****Table no. 6 standard calibration curve of curcumin**

Concentration	Abs.
2 µg/ml	0.195
4 µg/ml	0.41
6 µg/ml	0.648
8 µg/ml	0.955
10 µg/ml	1.25

Figure 7: Images of optimised formulations from 8-17

Results of Percentage Drug release and swelling index of optimised formulations are shown below.

Table No. 7: Percentage Drug release and swelling index optimised formulations

Run	Factor 1 A: HPMC (in mg)	Factor 2 B: EC (in mg)	Factor 3 C: DBP (in ml)	Response1 % Drug Release	Response2 Swelling Index
1	468.179	100	1	70.5	23.0 ± 0.2
2	200	50	0.5	79.7	21.5 ± 0.3
3	300	184.09	1	70.7	24.0 ± 0.2
4	400	150	0.5	72.7	25.2 ± 0.2
5	300	100	1	83.2	24.10 ± 1.4
6	300	100	1.8409	70.7	24.0 ± 0.2
7	300	100	1	83.2	24.10 ± 1.4
8	300	15.9104	1	77.2	20.4 ± 2.3
9	200	50	1.5	79.7	21.5 ± 0.3
10	400	50	0.5	76.2	22.34 ± 1.9
11	300	100	0.1591	68.7	24.20 ± 1.6
12	200	150	0.5	70.8	24.0 ± 0.1
13	200	150	1.5	70.4	22.34 ± 1.9
14	400	50	1.5	72.7	25.2 ± 0.4
15	400	150	1.5	72.4	24.0 ± 0.2
16	131.821	100	1	66.4	21.5 ± 0.3
17	300	100	1	83.2	24.10 ± 1.4

Table No. 8 Evaluation parameter of Optimised Formulations.

Run	Factor 1 A:HPMC (in mg)	Factor 2 B:EC (in mg)	Factor 3 C:DBP (in ml)	Response1 Drug Release	Response2 Swelling Index	Folding endurance ± SD	Tensile strength ± SD	Thickness ± SD	Drug content ± SD	% Moisture content ± SD	% Moisture uptake ± SD
1	468.179	100	1	70.5	23.0 ± 0.2	11.4 ± 0.2	0.356 ± 0.03	0.18± 0.2	95.6 ± 0.3	4.0 ± 0.2	25.03 ± 0.4
2	200	50	0.5	79.7	21.5 ± 0.3	11.7 ± 0.3	0.388 ± 0.03	0.16± 0.3	97.4 ± 0.6	3.5 ± 0.8	20.5 ± 0.3
3	300	184.09	1	70.7	24.0 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.3	0.342 ± 0.03	0.17± 0.4	98.3 ± 1.2	2.3 ± 0.2	20.12 ± 0.8
4	400	150	0.5	72.7	25.2 ± 0.2	11.6 ± 1.3	0.356 ± 0.03	0.18± 0.2	96.4 ± 0.2	4.0 ± 0.6	17.4 ± 0.2
5	300	100	1	83.2	24.10 ± 1.4	11.5 ± 0.2	0.372 ± 0.03	0.20± 0.3	98.1 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.6	17.2 ± 0.4
6	300	100	1.8409	70.7	24.0 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.3	0.342 ± 0.03	0.16± 0.3	96.1 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.4	16.8 ± 0.6
7	300	100	1	83.2	24.10 ± 1.4	11.5 ± 0.2	0.372 ± 0.03	0.20± 0.3	98.1 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.6	17.2 ± 0.4
8	300	15.9104	1	77.2	20.4 ± 2.3	13.1 ± 3.4	0.366 ± 0.05	0.18± 0.1	94.4 ± 0.4	4.0 ± 0.1	20.3 ± 0.4
9	200	50	1.5	79.7	21.5 ± 0.3	11.7 ± 0.3	0.388 ± 0.03	0.19± 0.2	99.2 ± 0.3	4.0 ± 0.3	20.5 ± 0.3
10	400	50	0.5	76.2	22.34 ± 1.9	13.1± 3.4	0.348 ± 0.07	0.18± 0.1	96.4 ± 0.8	2.5 ± 0.4	17.6 ± 0.3
11	300	100	0.159104	68.7	24.20 ± 1.6	12 ± 3.4	0.368 ± 0.03	0.18± 0.1	95.8 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.2	20.1 ± 1.2
12	200	150	0.5	70.8	24.0 ± 0.1	12.2 ± 0.3	0.342 ± 0.03	0.17± 0.4	97.4 ± 0.4	2.7 ± 0.4	20.12 ± 0.6
13	200	150	1.5	70.4	22.34 ± 1.9	13.1± 3.4	0.358 ± 0.03	0.18± 0.1	96.4 ± 0.8	2.5 ± 0.4	17.6 ± 0.3
14	400	50	1.5	72.7	25.2 ± 0.4	11.6 ± 1.3	0.362 ± 0.05	0.18± 0.2	96.4 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.2	17.4 ± 0.2
15	400	150	1.5	72.4	24.0 ± 0.2	12.2± 3.4	0.342 ± 0.03	0.17± 0.4	97.4 ± 0.6	2.5 ± 0.4	16.8 ± 0.6
16	131.821	100	1	66.4	21.5 ± 0.3	11.7 ± 0.3	0.388 ± 0.03	0.16± 0.3	98.2 ± 0.3	4.0 ± 0.3	20.5 ± 0.3
17	300	100	1	83.2	24.10 ± 1.4	11.5 ± 0.2	0.372 ± 0.03	0.20± 0.3	98.1 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.6	17.2 ± 0.4

Optimization of batch by QbD

Input variables and responses, experimental design, experimental execution, and statistical analysis and formulation optimization are critical parameters of statistical design. Collective effect of process variables, ie. polymer concentration; HPMC and EC with DBP as a percentage of elongation and drug release; dependent variables were analyzed using a Central Composite design.

Table No. 9: Build Information

File Version	12.0.1.0
Study Type	Response Surface
Design Type	Central composite design
Design Model	Quadratic
Build Time (ms)	1
Subtype	Randomized
Runs	17
Blocks	No Blocks

Table No. 10: Factors

Factor	Name	Units	Type	Minimum	Maximum	Coded Low	Coded High	Mean	Std. Dev.
A	HPMC	mg	Numeric	131.82	468.18	-1 ↔ 200.00	+1 ↔ 400.00	300.00	92.39
B	EC	mg	Numeric	15.91	184.09	-1 ↔ 50.00	+1 ↔ 150.00	100.00	46.19
C	DBP	ml	Numeric	0.1591	1.84	-1 ↔ 0.50	+1 ↔ 1.50	1.00	0.4619

Table No. 11: Responses

Response	Name	Units	Observations	Analysis	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Ratio	Transform	Model
R1	R1 Drug release	%	17	Polynomial	72.3	84.3	77.57	3.92	1.17	None	Quadratic
R2	R2 Swelling Index	%	17	Polynomial	21.5	25.2	23.43	1.16	1.17	None	2FI

Warning: The Cubic model is aliased.

Analysis of Drug Release

To examine the fit of the models for various polynomial models, e.g. interactive, cubic, quadratic

and linear and statistical test, ie. successive sum of squares of the model, experimental data were fitted and a summary model was prepared (Table 7.11)

Fit Summary

Table No. 12: Response 1: R1 Drug release

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.4525	0.0928	0.0127	0.2237	
2FI	0.8082	0.0748	0.1999	0.8864	
Quadratic	0.0023	0.3081	0.7591	0.7431	Suggested
Cubic	0.3081		0.8845		Aliased

ANOVA for Reduced Quadratic model

Table No. 13 Response 1: R1 Drug release

Model	346.79	6	57.8	5.88	0.0074
A-HPMC	9.64	1	9.64	0.9801	0.3455
B-EC	101.45	1	101.45	10.32	0.0093
C-DBP	2.54	1	2.54	0.2588	0.622
A ²	86.26	1	86.26	8.77	0.0142
B ²	64.66	1	64.66	6.58	0.0282
C ²	195.35	1	195.35	19.87	0.0012
Residual	98.33	10	9.83		
Lack of Fit	94.78	8	11.85	6.68	0.1367
Pure Error	3.55	2	1.77		
Cor Total	445.12	16			

Factor coding is **Coded**.

Sum of squares is **Type III - Partial**

The **Model F-value** of 5.88 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.74% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise.

P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case B, A², B², C² are significant model terms.

Table No. 14 Fit Statistics

Std. Dev.	1.92	R²	0.8946
Mean	77.57	Adjusted R²	0.7591
C.V. %	2.48	Predicted R²	0.7431
		Adeq Precision	7.7730

The Predicted R^2 of 0.7431 is as close to the Adjusted R^2 of 0.7591 i.e. the difference is not more than 0.2. Adeq Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Your ratio of 7.773 indicates an adequate signal. This model can be used to navigate the design space.

Final Equation in Terms of Actual Factors

R_1 Drug release = $35.90 + 0.174373 \text{ HPMC} + 0.137086 \text{ EC} + 32.43842 \text{ DBP} - 0.00028 \text{ HPMC}^2 - 0.00096 \text{ EC}^2 - 16.6509 \text{ DBP}^2$

The equation in terms of actual factors can be used to make predictions about the response for given levels of each factor. Here, the levels should be specified in the original units for each factor. This equation should not be used to determine the relative impact of each factor because the coefficients are scaled to accommodate the units of each factor and the intercept is not at the center of the design space.

RT Drug release

Color points by value of
RT Drug release:
68.1 84.3

RT Drug release

Color points by value of
RT Drug release:
68.1 84.3

R1 Drug release

Color points by value of R1 Drug release:
69.1 84.3

R1 Drug release

Color points by value of R1 Drug release:
69.1 84.3

R1 Drug release

Color points by value of R1 Drug release:
69.1 84.5

Factor Coding: Actual
● Design Points
--- 95% CI Bands

X1 = A: HPMC

Actual Factors
B: IC = 100
C: DBP = 1

Factor Coding: Actual

Actual factors
 A: HPMC = 300
 B: EC = 120
 C: DBP = 1

Factor Coding: Actual

● Design Points
 85.1 84.3

X1 = A: HPMC
 X2 = B: EC

Actual Factor
 C: DBP = 1

R1 Drug release

Color points by value of R1 Drug release:
66.1 68.1 70.1 72.1 74.1

Factor Coding: Actual

Design Points:
● Above Surface
○ Below Surface
66.1 68.1 70.1 72.1 74.1

X1 = A: HPMC
X2 = B: EC

Actual Factor
C: D₅₀ = 1

3D Surface

Figure 8: Final Equation in Terms of Actual Factors

Analysis of Swelling Index

To examine the fit of the models to different polynomial models, e.g., interactive, cubic, quadratic, and linear, and a statistical test, i.e., sum of squares of

the sequential model, experimental data were fitted and a summary model was constructed.

Fit Summary

Table No. 15 Response 2: R2 Swelling Index

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.6045		0.0731	0.6077	
2FI	0.0677		0.5552	0.5655	Suggested
Quadratic	0.5209		0.2559	1.5014	
Cubic			1		Aliased

ANOVA for Quadratic model**Table No. 16 Response 2: R2 Swelling Index**

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	11.96	6	1.99	2.12	0.1409	not significant
A-HPMC	0.0286	1	0.0286	0.0303	0.8652	
B-EC	0.2346	1	0.2346	0.2492	0.6285	
C-DBP	2.48	1	2.48	2.63	0.136	
AB	1.5	1	1.5	1.59	0.236	
AC	0.0004	1	0.0004	0.0005	0.983	
BC	7.72	1	7.72	8.2	0.0168	
Residual	9.42	10	0.9415			
Lack of Fit	9.42	8	1.18			
Pure Error	0	2	0			
Cor Total	21.37	16				

Factor coding is **Coded**.

Sum of squares is **Type III - Partial**

Factor coding is Coded.

Sum of squares is Type III - Partial

The Model F-value of 2.12 implies the model is not significant relative to the noise. There is a 14.09%

chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise.

P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case BC is a significant model term. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. If there are many insignificant model terms (not counting those required to support hierarchy), model reduction may improve your model.

Table No. 17 Fit Statistics

Std. Dev.	0.9703	R²	0.5595
Mean	23.43	Adjusted R²	0.5552
C.V. %	4.14	Predicted R²	0.5655
		Adeq Precision	6.0596

A negative Predicted R² implies that the overall mean may be a better predictor of your response than the current model. In some cases, a higher order model may also predict better.

Adeq Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Your ratio of 6.060 indicates an adequate signal. This model can be used to navigate the design space.

Final Equation in Terms of Actual Factors

$$\begin{aligned} R2 \text{ Swelling Index} = & 9.42975 + 0.05146\text{HPMC} + \\ & 0.122608 \text{EC} + 0.564036 \text{DBP} - 0.000124\text{HPMC} * \text{EC} \\ & - 0.0036\text{HPMC} * \text{DBP} - 0.0318\text{EC} * \text{DBP} - \\ & 0.000065\text{HPMC}^2 - 0.000224\text{EC}^2 + 0.232389\text{DBP}^2 \end{aligned}$$

The equation in terms of actual factors can be used to make predictions about the response for given levels of each factor. Here, the levels should be specified in the original units for each factor. This equation should not be used to determine the relative impact of each factor because the coefficients are scaled to accommodate the units of each factor and the intercept is not at the centre of the design space.

R2 Swelling Index

Color points by value of R2 Swelling Index
20.4 23.2

R2 Swelling Index
 Color coded by value of
 R2 Swelling Index
 (1) (2) (3)

Factor Coding: Actual

Actual Factors
 A: HPMC = 300
 B: EC = 100
 C: DGF = 1

Factor Coding: Actual

● Design Points
 --- Site (2, 3, 4, 5)

(1) = A: HPMC

Actual Factors
 B: EC = 100
 C: DGF = 1

Factor Coding: Actual
 Design Points
 20.4 25.2
 X1 = A: HPMC
 X2 = B: EC
 Actual Factor
 C: DSP = 1

R2 Sewling Index
 Color points for values of
 R2 Sewling Index
 20.4 25.2

Factor Coding: Actual
 Design Points
 20.4 25.2
 X1 = A: HPMC
 X2 = B: EC
 Actual Factor
 C: DSP = 1

Figure 10 Final Equation in Terms of Actual Factors

Optimization

Table No. 18 Constraints

Name	Goal	Lower Limit	Upper Limit	Lower Weight	Upper Weight	Importance
A:HPMC	is in range	200	400	1	1	3
B:EC	is in range	50	150	1	1	3
C:DBP	is in range	0.5	1.5	1	1	3
R1 Drug release	none	72.3	84.3	1	1	3
R2 Sewlling Index	none	21.5	25.2	1	1	3

Table No. 19 Solutions

Number	HPMC	EC	DBP	R1 Drug release	R2 Swelling Index	Desirability	
1	313.008	107.008	1.164	82.85	23.245	1	Selected
2	400	50	1.5	75.193	24.231	1	
3	300	100	1	83.465	23.426	1	
4	200	150	1.5	75.693	22.634	1	
5	400	150	0.5	74.246	24.494	1	
6	200	50	0.5	79.355	22.344	1	
7	400	50	0.5	77.901	23.132	1	
8	200	50	1.5	78.948	23.472	1	
9	200	150	0.5	72	25.436	1	
10	220.649	89.768	0.777	82.331	23.463	1	
11	370.809	117.571	1.419	79.525	22.681	1	
12	396.019	115.064	0.589	78.941	23.895	1	
13	283.01	126.421	0.633	79.311	24.234	1	
14	370.768	72.568	0.741	81.768	23.434	1	

15	264.276	63.209	0.594	81.587	22.988	1	
16	249.472	108.826	1.05	82.853	23.452	1	
17	257.605	81.045	1.005	83.816	23.326	1	
18	386.864	93.707	0.83	81.832	23.522	1	
19	389.907	66.592	0.902	81.503	23.513	1	
20	316.165	139.265	0.883	80.219	23.748	1	
21	208.723	99.086	0.63	80.18	23.755	1	
22	318.903	132.116	1.034	81.383	23.378	1	
23	262.254	134.221	0.536	76.797	24.661	1	
24	213.425	90.156	0.845	82.589	23.436	1	
25	334.584	74.333	1.025	83.211	23.423	1	
26	394.986	67.92	1.402	78.323	23.721	1	
27	352.995	142.62	1.285	79.382	22.595	1	
28	205.431	61.994	1.126	82.864	23.141	1	
29	278.524	58.191	0.891	83.339	23.162	1	
30	209.263	97.022	0.534	79.087	23.772	1	
31	313.363	59.056	1.277	81.649	23.569	1	
32	268.742	56.623	0.572	81.242	22.842	1	
33	216.824	52.34	0.994	82.94	22.99	1	
34	310.816	66.394	1.125	83.067	23.423	1	
35	361.433	147.803	0.867	78.877	23.635	1	
36	212.515	127.457	1.499	78.416	22.788	1	
37	313.675	125.321	1.397	80.33	22.722	1	
38	296.612	103.762	1.284	82.412	23.155	1	
39	284.424	107.163	1.176	82.914	23.262	1	
40	249.731	89.682	0.857	83.256	23.44	1	
41	335.662	137.097	1.157	80.686	23.029	1	
42	389.015	52.594	1.311	78.538	23.936	1	
43	345.996	73.538	1.204	82.189	23.478	1	
44	328.122	58.121	0.897	82.787	23.324	1	
45	399.621	96.835	0.796	81.249	23.551	1	
46	373.987	101.82	1.288	81.107	23.116	1	
47	370.385	128.934	1.462	78.497	22.37	1	

48	290.334	69.231	1.204	82.984	23.397	1	
49	223.525	90.545	0.761	82.241	23.485	1	
50	321.503	138.644	0.84	80.045	23.825	1	
51	301.483	79.49	1.377	81.663	23.357	1	
52	248.954	77.067	1.132	83.549	23.295	1	
53	376.48	69.157	0.917	82.062	23.485	1	
54	212.84	140.036	0.912	78.71	24.084	1	
55	266.494	72.414	0.791	83.265	23.239	1	
56	366.512	66.216	1.388	79.493	23.682	1	
57	310.773	113.793	1.185	82.474	23.186	1	
58	392.733	108.203	0.651	80.037	23.754	1	
59	266.837	55.776	0.816	83.041	23.034	1	
60	342.221	108.695	1.33	81.354	23.002	1	
61	206.321	75.358	0.799	82.54	23.178	1	
62	359.121	92.857	0.935	82.817	23.454	1	
63	371.031	104.739	1.462	79.324	22.892	1	
64	274.628	99.001	1.326	82.278	23.169	1	
65	308.499	85.525	1.492	80.257	23.255	1	
66	302.272	59.986	1.128	82.898	23.42	1	
67	356.281	143.877	0.815	79.089	23.779	1	
68	216.27	107.566	1.018	82.337	23.518	1	
69	382.793	97.417	1.198	81.528	23.249	1	
70	332.618	115.86	1.219	81.996	23.084	1	
71	206.859	147.28	1.126	78.144	23.634	1	
72	277.414	144.859	1.182	79.805	23.166	1	
73	308.213	55.182	1.233	81.873	23.549	1	
74	389.259	66.478	1.054	81.325	23.58	1	
75	283.406	61.623	1.407	80.864	23.546	1	
76	203.161	123.461	0.615	77.649	24.405	1	
77	250.122	63.59	1.44	80.745	23.454	1	
78	339.838	75.557	0.703	82.237	23.397	1	
79	387.461	80.676	1.271	80.628	23.453	1	
80	386.763	50.469	0.956	80.652	23.58	1	

81	265.896	110.748	0.792	81.997	23.766	1	
82	356.417	65.325	0.904	82.478	23.43	1	
83	288.135	83.786	0.972	83.821	23.378	1	
84	289.182	124.37	0.792	81.091	23.894	1	
85	326.64	73.817	1.082	83.207	23.42	1	
86	235.687	64.343	1.033	83.499	23.182	1	
87	291.595	108.218	1.16	82.919	23.269	1	
88	365.245	104.544	1.145	82.169	23.232	1	
89	305.654	50.698	1.383	80.112	23.733	1	
90	347.39	101.284	0.927	82.846	23.469	1	
91	330.69	121.867	1.287	81.281	22.92	1	
92	202.349	119.096	1.194	81.013	23.374	1	
93	237.348	74.699	1.186	83.224	23.279	1	
94	349.428	123.08	0.729	80.567	23.844	1	
95	207.472	142.385	1.313	78.3	23.135	1	
96	312.14	88.316	0.882	83.465	23.449	1	
97	261.407	132.372	1.263	80.669	23.08	1	
98	248.218	129.004	1.155	81.193	23.349	1	
99	324.047	97.831	0.896	83.186	23.494	1	
100	356.393	134.625	0.534	77.209	24.356	1	

Table No. 20: Factors

Factor	Name	Level	Low Level	High Level	Std. Dev.	Coding
A	HPMC	313.01	200.00	400.00	0.0000	Actual
B	EC	107.01	50.00	150.00	0.0000	Actual
C	DBP	1.16	0.5000	1.50	0.0000	Actual

Two-sided Confidence = 95% Population = 99%

Table No. 21: Point Prediction

Solution 1 of 100 Response	Predicted Mean	Predicted Median	Observed	Std Dev	SE Mean	95% CI low for Mean	95% CI high for Mean	95% TI low for 99% Pop	95% TI high for 99% Pop
R1 Drug release	82.8496	82.8496		1.9231	1.07364	80.3108	85.3884	71.9132	93.786
R2 Swelling Index	23.2449	23.2449		0.97033	0.25663	22.673	23.8167	18.798	27.6917

Confirmation Location #1

CONCLUSION

The study focused on developing and optimizing Curcumin transdermal patches using Central Composite Design to evaluate the effects of formulation variables on drug release and swelling index. Preformulation studies confirmed the drug's authenticity and properties, including UV absorption maxima at 425 nm. The optimized patch (F5: 300 mg HPMC, 100 mg EC, 1 mL DBP) showed 83.2% drug release and a swelling index of 24.10 ± 1.4 . Drug release increased with higher DBP and decreased with more hydrophobic EC, while swelling improved with higher HPMC concentrations. The results highlight the feasibility of Curcumin patches for sustained drug release, better patient compliance, and improved treatment for inflammation and allergies, with potential as an alternative to conventional therapies.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

There are no conflicts of interest.

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